

Road to Dynamic Functional Split in Radio Access Networks

Ricardo J. B. Pousa*, Giang T. Nguyen^{†‡}, Riccardo Bassoli^{*‡}, Frank H. P. Fitzek^{*‡}

**Deutsche Telekom Chair of Communication Networks, TU Dresden, Germany*

[†]*Haptic Communication Systems, TU Dresden, Germany*

[‡]*Centre for Tactile Internet with Human-in-the-Loop (CeTI), TU Dresden, Germany*

E-mails: {ricardo.pousa|giang.nguyen|riccardo.bassoli|frank.fitzek}@tu-dresden.de

Abstract—The ever-growing bandwidth requirements of mobile networks have prompted the re-evaluation of a centralized architecture for Radio Access Networks (RANs). Although relieved by optical connections, the bottleneck inherent with C-RANs can impede future service delivery. Changing to a non-static functional architecture may be better suited for evolving scenarios. Different options have been outlined to split the Base Band Units (BBUs) protocol stack functionality to meet the envisioned demands while minimizing Capital Expenditure (CAPEX). The bandwidth requirement between split functions varies greatly depending on the Functional Split (FS) chosen. The emergence of Network Function Virtualization (NFV), and the possibility of using Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components with specialized software allows for easy repair and maintainability. By deploying BBU functions virtually on COTS nodes, enabling the architecture adjustment on a use-case basis, Operating Expenditure (OPEX) can be further reduced. This work covers the solution of Dynamic Functional Split (DFS), the deployment requirements, and how they affect the envisioned RAN architecture. The conclusion reached is that addressing the needs of the emergent mobile networks with a DFS unlocks new opportunities for using RAN resources.

Index Terms—Radio Access Networks, Dynamic Functional Split, Software Defined Networks, Network Function Virtualization

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of 5G, mobile networks have been veering towards complete software-defined operation. An architecture based on Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) hosted in a central processing node led to deploying mobile networks with a cloud architecture harboring core and baseband units (BBUs) functionalities. This architectural shift, enabled by improvements in fiber optic connections, helped reduce the number of on-site installations of processing resources and opened the road for features like Coordinated Multipoint transmission.

Now, this architecture is being put into question for some use cases where the front-haul links between BBU and Radio Resource Heads (RRH) using IQ signals digitalization (CPRI) would require prohibitive bandwidths [1]. Additionally, latency and jitter become concerns as the Hybrid Automatic Repeat Request (HARQ) imposes further stringent conditions with acknowledge mode transmissions. These factors will limit the deployment of the BBU pool serving an RRH to a distance that could ensure a 250 μ s one-way latency [2].

To extend the possible deployments it has been proposed the splitting of BBU functionalities, in this paper it is considered

that the split unit hosting functionalities closer to the core can be identified as the Central Unit (CU), the Distributed Unit (DU) will harbour the remaining functionalities near the RRH, and if any functionality is further split from DU for another unit it can be identified by the term Radio Unit (RU). The benefit of splitting is that the requirements for the link connecting CU and DU can be relaxed depending on the amount of functionalities set at the DU, e.g. a split that places HARQ at the DU could relax latency requirements for that link.

With full virtualization of the units above, it is possible to distribute the functionalities they implement to general-purpose processing nodes. If the allocation of units is done in run time, the RAN deployment can further support the dynamic minimization of energy consumption or the adjustment of data rates at the aggregation nodes whilst delivering the settled-upon services. To the best of our knowledge, there is no example of this paradigm of operation realized in commercial-grade 5G deployments. The outlook for future 5G small cell deployments so far [3] will be comprised of All-in-one (GnodeB), two-unit (CU-DU), three-unit (CU-DU-RU), and distributed antenna systems. The paradigm of operation for all of these forecast deployments is static. Jointly, it has also outlined four key barriers to their deployments: lack of scalability, limited cooperation, uncertainty over the choice of architecture, and uncertainty if it is a future-proof investment. These barriers to investment can be addressed with a dynamic operation of the network and the infrastructure necessary to support it. This infrastructure would comprise Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) components, mitigating scalability and cooperation issues, while the Software Defined Networks (SDNs) and NFV will ease the architecture change. Towards future-proofing the network, the move to a full Virtualized RAN (VRAN) with COTS components will ensure that the accessibility in the scaling of resources and any future needs can be met. The dynamic functional split seeks to improve the dynamic operation of a VRAN further, enabling the change of functional architecture during runtime.

This paper explores the contributions shaping a virtual GnodeB and how these enable the dynamic split deployment of functionalities replacing a BBU pool associated with a Centralized Radio Access Network (C-RAN). It briefly covers *5G and Beyond requirements* and the suitability of a dynamic

RAN. It also explores the *Functional Split* and how the contributions have narrowed down the best candidate splits. From the chosen splits, it presents an architecture that seeks to converge multiple interface standards. Following the definition of the *VGnodeB architecture* it presents the concept enabled by it, the *Dynamic Functional Split*, its challenges, and steps to deploy it practically. Finally, it surveys the requirements and recommendations for deploying a *Virtual RAN* architecture that would enable the Dynamic Functional Split, with the added benefits expected from it and new opportunities.

The remaining article is organized as follows: Section II summarizes the requirements of 5G systems. Next, we describe functional splits and gNodeB in Sections III and IV, respectively. After summarizing the dynamic functional split approaches in Section V, we discuss their implications on virtual RAN in Section VI. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section VII.

II. 5G AND BEYOND REQUIREMENTS

This section highlights essential scenarios and services for 5G and beyond systems. Subsequently, we discuss the system's radio access network (RAN) requirements. 5G systems aim to support three main types of services: enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB), ultra-reliable low-latency communication (uRLLC), and massive machine-type communication (mMTC) [6]. The fast-paced advancements of 5G focused on the assurance of communication for significantly different requirements for each type of service. However, even within these types of services, there is a great variety of requirements for their scenarios.

The most demanding identified 5G scenarios cover a diverse range of high data rates and traffic densities, as described in [7]. The document defines the expected data rate for Downlink (DL) and Uplink (UL), area traffic capacity for DL and UL, overall user density, activity factor, UE speed, and coverage. From the scenarios covered with high data rate and traffic density (Table 7.1-1), the key differences are that the experienced data rate DL varies from 15Mb/s for Airplane connectivity to 1 Gb/s for indoor hotspots, UL area traffic capacity will range from 500 Mb/s/km² to 7,5 Tb/s/km² for Rural Macro and Broadband access in a crowd respectively, and activity factors from 20% to 50% of high-speed vehicles.

The diversity of requirements for the most demanding identified scenarios can be supported with on-time allocation of resources. This allocation should be done according to tidal shifts in usage [8] or per the impromptu shifts in the most volatile scenarios [9]. Therefore, the required orchestration needs to be agile and should have an all-encompassing view of the network, characteristic of centralized control of SDN. SDNs and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) enable the dynamic real-time orchestration of mobile networks. This concept could be seen with FlexRAN [10], that through COTS components with purposely developed software and the additional control offered by SDN, it is possible to deploy a RAN with minimal purpose-built components. A RAN devoid of specialized hardware, as much as possible, will lead to

reduced OPEX, faster repairs and deployments [11], and less time to market for new features. As such a C-RAN architecture, where a BBU pool performs most of the processing and communicates through CPRI with RRHs, comes with significant ease of orchestration and efficient operation due to the collocation of computing resources. However, due to the centralization, the necessity to transmit a substantial amount of additional information arises. The amount of information will escalate proportionally with factors such as the number of radio antennas, the number of subcarriers employed, and the samples used for the cyclic prefix per IQ sample to be sent. As such for a given experienced data rate on the user end, from Long Term Evolutions' (LTE) distributed architecture to 5Gs' centralized architecture, the fronthaul link from the central office (CO) or the BBU pools' to the RRH would have to support bandwidths up to 50 times greater [2]. Additionally, the length of the link is also a limitation, due to timing requirements, it is considered that the maximum length of the link between a BBU and its serving RRH should be kept under 20km [12].

Multiple options have been proposed for the functional splitting of the protocol stack implemented by a BBU to deploy networks that support the defined scenarios while easing the architectural restrictions. Splitting the functionality for scenarios such as rural macro connectivity will lead to increased reach for the link, allowing for the best positioning of RRH, and ensuring modest DL and UL UE experienced data rates (50Mb/s and 25Mb/s). On the other hand, in scenarios such as Broadband Access in a Crowd, where the density of User Equipments is expected to significantly increase UL BW requirements, the functional splitting could decrease BW necessary in the serving link.

III. FUNCTIONAL SPLITS

Functional splitting can address some of the limitations of the current architecture for specific 5G-supported scenarios. However, where to split generally has to balance two key aspects: overhead information and the increase in processing resources. The more centralized the processing, the more overhead information must be sent towards RRH, while the opposite would require increased processing resources at/near the RRH. The functional splitting in 5G and beyond seeks to find a balance between these two modes of operation while enabling features such as Carrier Aggregation, Cross Carrier Scheduling, High Order MIMO, and Coordinated Multipoint [4]. The Functional Split refers to the split of BBU functionality, separated into different units. In this paper, it is considered that with a single split, the different units would be the centralized Unit (CU) and Distributed Unit (DU); if a consecutive split is also employed, there would be a third unit, considered to be the Radio Unit (RU). This operation paradigm has been spearheaded by organizations such as the Open-RAN Alliance, Next Generation Mobile Networks Alliance, Small Cell Forum (SCF), and 3GPP through the standardization of interfaces. However, the protocol stack functions that are divided between these units differ from organization to organization. Figure

Fig. 1. Functional splits considered in this paper (Redrawn from 3GPP: [2], SCF: [4], O-RAN [5]).

1 shows the proposed splits by 3GPP, with the added 7.2x proposed by the Open RAN alliance. While almost every split would have advantages and disadvantages, the ones with defined interfaces have been chosen with specific use cases in mind. The following are the splits considered to have a mature interface, hence being better candidates for developing a VNodeB solution supporting them.

A. OSI Layer 2 Split

Within Layer 2, split 2 establishes that the Central Unit will harbour Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP), and the remaining BBU functionality will be delegated to DU. If the control and user plane are separated, this split can be implemented with an F1 interface between CU and DU, where F1-C would connect the control plane and F1-U user plane. This split increases link length with timing requirements being more lax than lower layer splits, such as splits four and beyond due to automatic repeat requests. The split also extends the control and user plane separation till the DU. Support for this split originated from LTE Dual Connectivity. For 5G, this split would allow for an extension of coverage for non-low-latency communications. As such, split 2 can be especially appropriate for specific long-range remote scenarios.

B. Inter Layer Split

Split 6s' proponent, SCF, has identified it as a good candidate due to the possibility of maintaining most of the interference mitigation features while enabling Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) and Application-specific integrated circuit (ASIC) implementation of DU tackling the more computational intensive physical layer functions. This split would move RLC and MAC to the CU and the physical layer stack to the DU. By colocating RLC and MAC for multiple DUs, it becomes feasible to implement mitigation techniques among RRHs served by these DUs. The interface for this split, Functional Application Platform Interface (FAPI) was created to standardize communication between OSI layer two and one of the BBU protocol stack. The following improvement for communication using ethernet switched networks, nFAPI, assures implementation of split six with non-colocated processing units. nFAPI was created to connect small cells to a centralized core, assuming a previous C-RAN deployment,

the transition to a split 6 supporting joint transmission and scheduling can be an attractive proposition for extending a Mobile Network Operator (MNO) coverage with small cells, ideally for eMBB.

C. OSI Layer 1 Splits

Split 7.2 and 7.2x both use eCPRI to establish communication between CU and DU, but 7.2x differs by placing Resource Element Mapping of the Physical layer at the CU instead of DU and introduces optional UL and DL digital radio compression, (with subsequent decompression) [13]. These two splits are good candidates comparatively to split 8, providing an alternative solution with significant laxer BW requirements, up to 10 times less [14], while minimizing the added processing requirements downstream.

Split 8 is regarded as the C-RAN split, implemented with CPRI communication between RRH and BBU, it would eliminate the need for CU-DU architecture. Albeit with higher BW requirements than any other splits, it requires a one-way latency link comparable to that of splits after 6, depending on HARQ set timings. It's also the split that would enable the use of UL joint reception/equalization and High Order MIMO. These characteristics set it as the ideal split for uRLLC use cases, possibly even implemented with the optical link carrying radio signals to the RRH (Radio over Ethernet/Fiber [ROE/F]).

The defined interfaces open the road towards implementing a softwarized functional split. Interfaces can assure the full functionality of a GnodeB with a VNF approach subdivided virtual functions. In the following section, we present the architecture to realize functional splits. The goal is to merge each contribution with a clear division of units and further outline their requirements.

IV. VIRTUAL GNODEB ARCHITECTURE

The Virtual GnodeB architecture accommodates various splits, enabling its deployment with multiple combinations of components. For each implemented functional split, the VNodeB supports the interfaces for orchestration [5], side-link [15] and functional transmission. Figure 2 presents our proposed envisioned Virtualized GnodeB software architecture, unifying defined interfaces and functional splits. This

Fig. 2. VgNodeB Architecture combining elements from O-RAN [5], 3GPP [15], [16].

architecture identifies five units (4 of those indispensable), and five different splits: CU-CP and CU-UP delimited by split 2, DU-High implementing RLC and MAC of the protocol stack (delimited by split 2 and 6), DU-Low implementing the remainder of Physical Layer stack, interfacing with RU (splits 7.2/2x) or with an RRH with CPRI or ROF/E (split 8). Interfaces X2 and Xn are to be present to support side-link communication, with ENodeBs and GnodeBs, respectively, connecting to their corresponding Application Protocol (AP) and User Plane (U) services. E1 ensures the expected operation with the separation of planes by exchanging signalling information between components of a CU. Splitting CU into control and user plane components, allows for the detachment of user data flows from control data flows. As these flows have different requirements such as bandwidth and latency, by separating them it's possible to cater to the needs of each with different resources. For the Control plane, the

Next Generation Application Protocol (NGAP) will establish communication with the Access and Mobility Function of the 5G core. Regarding the User plane, the General Packet Radio Services Tunneling Protocol (GTP-U) ensures the secure user data exchange with the User Plane Function of the 5G core.

For orchestration, E2AP connects to Near Real Time RAN Intelligent Controllers (Near Real Time RIC) through E2, for immediate orchestration. On the other hand, O1 offers the Non-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controllers (Non-Real Time RIC) and Service Management Orchestration (SMO) the necessary interface for management. Both interfaces would relay KPI information, while O1 can also be used for software management and keeps track of heartbeat services. Towards the full virtualization of RAN, there have been three key open-source implementations emulating and simulating GnodeB functionalities: OpenAirInterface¹, srsRAN², and UERAN-SIM³. Of these three, the first two intend to provide multiple functional splits, with the first already implementing splits 2, 6, 7.2 and 8. Openairinterfaces' project is the closest open-source implementation to the proposed solution, implementing, to the best of our knowledge, split 7.2 using Open FrontHaul over eCPRI [17].

Overall it should be possible to run a VgNodeB with every identified functional split [18], with each split component in different physical processing units, using containers or virtual machines to ease portability. The use of virtualization for functionalities within RAN assumes that there is some level of in-network computing resources and a C-RAN architecture has been adapted towards it. The computing resources should be decided upon if a Dynamic Functional Split (DFS) is to be supported.

V. DYNAMIC FUNCTIONAL SPLIT

Dynamic Functional Splitting in VRANs is enabled by a VgNodeB implementing multiple functional splits, the deployment of edge computing nodes and dynamic control over both. In high data rate scenarios with non-real-time latency requirements, distributing processing tasks to nodes closer to RRH (DU/RU), would reduce BW requirement in the upstream link. However such scenarios exhibit an activity factor of no more than 50%, resulting in suboptimal resource allocation if statically set. With a DFS, on low-tide periods the split can be changed to centralized processing, increasing processing efficiency. This adaptive approach where close-to-the-RRH nodes can be set to idle operation, or freed for other applications will optimise operation over a constant uncongested link. Integrating DFS and end-to-end slicing is also a promising solution to tackle simultaneous scenarios served by a single RRH/RU [19]. For URLLC an end-to-end slice with full centralization should be used, reducing the number of processing node hops and therefore added transport latency. If there is an increase in BW requirements for concurrent non-URLLC services, that compromise URLLC services, adjusting

¹<https://gitlab.eurecom.fr/oai/openairinterface5g>

²https://github.com/srsran/srsran_project

³<https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>

the split for the slices of non-URLLC services will alleviate BW requirements. Ensuring the continuity of URLLC service without overprovisioning link capacity.

The simulation of such aforementioned scenarios and more, with full virtualization of GnodeB components and their migration, have been explored with different optimization goals: energy efficiency through centralization [20], [21], latency [22], interference management [23], and minimization of OPEX [24] [25].

The deployment of a Dynamic Functional Split presupposes that the underlying infrastructure to support the possible splits of inter-connected VNodeB units is in place, but also that there are protocols to perform the migration of said components in run-time. These protocols would have to ensure the recovery of states of these components, implemented in virtual machines or containers, performing the transmission of the states to the new hosting processing node. The migration process for units of VNodeBs is still an open research question, as doing it without affecting a user's service is highly challenging. Towards this goal [26], [27] have implemented solutions that seek to mitigate the loss of service, while minimizing additional latency for a user.

From both works it is outlined the key challenge of the split migration procedure having to be designed per combination of splits, i.e. 6 to 8, 2 to 8 as they would require the re-establishment of different types of connections and the transmission of different state information such as buffer contents. Another challenge yet untackled is the security of these migration procedures, where, for example, the migration of buffers of User Data and Control Data hosted on PDCP, RLC and MAC must be done without compromising their contents. The security and missing standards [28] for migration can be expected to be addressed with existing technologies and further standardization, with alterations applied via software updates on already deployed nodes. The challenge of when to split is a problem usually formulated as a form of Integer Linear Programming, to tackle it, the previously cited works used different algorithms such as Lyapunov [21], Markov chain [22] and Heuristic-based algorithms [24] [25]. This decision can be considered to be a problem of dynamic allocation of resources, and with it being an open question in other areas of research, it is also for DFS. The resource allocation challenge will depend on the goal/policies set for optimizing the network, where appropriate consideration to BW minimization, processing efficiency, interference features support and multiple service slices coexistence must be included in the deployment of solutions. The enforcement of a policy set for resource allocation is expected to be integrated with management systems (SMO and SDN controller).

Having set the challenges for DFS implementation, it must be emphasized the advantages it brings. The flexibility of operation can lead to future-proofing the network. The shift towards full virtualization brings software development cycles to the upgrade of functionalities. The use-case-to-use-case adjustment will inevitably improve energy efficiency. Overall, the elements that are encompassed by a VRAN make way

for a DFS operation, be it the defined required hardware or the developments in software resulting in VNFs. The missing elements are the migration-related features, that can bolster the dynamic operation of a VRAN. For this paradigm shift in RAN operation, several key points must be followed for its deployment.

VI. VIRTUAL RAN REQUIREMENTS

The architecture envisioned assumes that every processing unit (CU, DU, RU) will have in-network processing resources susceptible to being allocated. These resources should be comprised of COTS components akin to the O-RAN specification [29] [30], connected preferably through optical fiber links. Comparatively to a C-RAN with fronthaul switched or point-to-point deployment [31], the VRAN would veer toward fully optically switched xhaul [32]. This xhaul would encompass: the underlying nodes linking core or mobile network user data gateway till their terminations (RRHs/RU). The deployment of co/near-located processing resources should be done if the node performs aggregation, or with regards to timing requirements of their intended purpose for the majority of the operational time (CU/DU-H/DU-L). Resulting in the preferred topology of the network to be deployed would be star or mesh networks, as opposed to ring-based networks [33]. The scaling of resources per aggregation node falls in line with the one-to-many consideration of xhaul downstream, as one CU should support multiple DUs, and one DU should support multiple RUs. The endpoints chosen (RRHs/RUs) will determine the standard used for communication, with the choice of CPRI the switching components will be restricted. As such endpoints that accept ROE (standard 1914.3) and eCPRI should be favoured, to be able to use general packet-switching components.

The existence of general purpose computing resources running VNFs and general ethernet switched connections in the xhaul means that concepts such as Multi-tenant operation [34] can be broadened beyond MNO sharing of infrastructure. This concept, enabled by SDN control over a VRAN, and the further close to the user computing resources, would also enable closer to the user edge computing applications, opening another vector of opportunities for MNOs, PNOs and neutral hosts. The presence of in-network computing resources and the means for controlling their allocation dynamically per VNF, not only paves the way for the dynamic change of functional split but can also enable energy-efficient adjustments (low-power mode and idling), which can be integrated into regular end-to-end operation in a VRAN.

VII. CONCLUSION

5G RANs deployed with SDN and NFV will have their control capabilities bolstered. The favored architecture, with a cloud/pool of processing resources, often leads to the centralization of functionalities. However, due to the different scenarios supported by 5G and beyond, this architecture's degree of centralization comes with shortcomings for demanding scenarios that can ultimately hinder their execution.

Ergo, a VRAN capable of dynamically adjusting its Functional Split depending on the scenario, is proposed. Deploying a VRAN supporting DFS may require additional investment in computational resources, but if done with COTS components hosting VNFs, further broadening a RAN's range of provided services becomes a reality.

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